

CASE COMMENT: SWISS RIBBONS PVT. LTD. VS. UNION OF INDIA

by

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INTRODUCTION:

‘The defaulter’s paradise is no longer obtainable. In its wake, the economy has reclaimed its instinctual prominence.’

-: Justice R F Nariman

The Apex Court affirmed the constitutional validity of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 in the landmark judgement of *Swiss Ribbons Pvt. Ltd. vs. Union of India*¹. The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code which had been enacted in the year 2016 was revolutionary in nature as it was implemented at a time when the non-performing assets crisis was at its peak. Therefore, the Code has paved the way for a comprehensive, integrated, and non-bifurcated insolvency and bankruptcy law that applies to corporate entities, enterprises, and individuals. The Code has culminated in a paradigm shift in assessing the sustainability of a corporation or declaring it a bad asset from “inability to pay the obligations” to “determining default.” The case comment delves into the rationale of the Hon’ble Court in constructing the judgement as the bedrock of this economic legislation and bankruptcy law in India. Furthermore, the case comment examines the obstacles in this Code and the Hon’ble Court’s advocacy for the Code from its inception, as well as underlining the fundamental points of contention.

FACTS:-

On 15th January 2019, a bench consisting of Justice R F Nariman and Navin Sinha had withheld orders on a few writ petitions and exceptional leave applications, including those which had been filed by the High Courts of Calcutta and Gujarat, challenging the constitutionality of the Code. There were a bunch of 10 petitions which had been recorded under the meticulous eye of the

¹ Swiss Ribbons Pvt. Ltd. vs. Union of India , 2019 3 SCR 535.

Supreme Court, primarily contending that the three-year-old law was discriminatory, unfair, and arbitrary, thus challenging the constitutional validity the Code.

ISSUES RAISED IN THE CASE-:

The primary issue arose regarding the constitutionality of the provisions which have been laid down under the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016. The following are the major issues which have been addressed in this landmark judgement-:

- 1) Whether the division of creditors into financial creditors and operational creditors violates the right to equality under Article 14 of the Constitution of India?
- 2) Whether the Committee of Creditors (COC) 90% approval criteria for investors withdrawing money under Section 12A of the Code is too excessive?
- 3) Whether Section 29A of the Code is an appropriate mechanism for identifying who is eligible for participating in the bankruptcy resolution process?
- 4) Whether Section 53 of the Code violates Article 14 of the Constitution of India?

CONTENTIONS RAISED BY THE PARTIES-:

ARGUMENTS RAISED BY APPELLANTS-:

Shri Mukul Rohatgi, learned senior counsel for the appellants had contented intelligible differentia between the financial creditors and operational creditors. The counsel for the appellants argued that the distinction between the two violates the right to equality which has been enshrined under Article 14 of the Constitution of India. They also contended that Section 12A of the Code grants the Committee of Creditors unfettered powers, thus permitting for arbitrary abuse, and placing the operational creditors at the mercy of the Committee of Creditors. The appellants raised the contention that Section 29A of the Code is arbitrary in nature as it enables the promoters the right to partake in the debt recovery process. Lastly, the appellants raised the contention that Section 53 of the Code is discriminatory and arbitrary in nature, thus violating Article 14 of the Indian Constitution.

ARGUMENTS RAISED BY RESPONDENTS-:

Shri K.K Venugopal, the learned Attorney General of India and Shri Tushar Mehta, learned Solicitor General for India had refuted all the contentions which had been raised by the appellants. They contended that the intelligible differentia between financial and operational creditors stems from the nature of the contracts inked, wherein the financial contracts comprise of humongous sums of money and operational contracts comprise of modest sums of money. The differentiation between the two is incomprehensible, yet it is intently correlated to the objectives that the Code strives to accomplish. With respect to Section 12A of the Code, the learned counsel for the respondents argued that once the application of the creditor is acknowledged by the Adjudicating Authority, the proceeding becomes proceeding in rem, and thus the establishment of the Committee of Creditors is best outfitted to deal with applications for withdrawal or settlement after the admittance of an insolvency petition. The respondents contended that Section 29A of the Code is not retroactive in nature as it is intended at those who are otherwise ineligible to be in charge of a corporate debtor's administration, thus achieving one of the Code's foremost objectives. Lastly, the respondents contended that Section 53 of the Code which relates to the distribution of assets does not violate the right to equality enshrined under Article 14 of the Constitution of India.

RATIO DECIDENDI:-

The ratio decidendi in this momentous judgement has been laid down as follows:-

The aforementioned decision had been passed to uphold the constitutional validity of the Code in order to allow for a wide range of interpretations while accomplishing the objectives laid down under the Code. Through clarification on the procedural and the substantive aspect of the Code, the bench has endeavored to resolve a slew of concerns about the interpretation and the constitutionality of the Code.

JUDGEMENT:-

The Supreme Court on 25th January 2019 upheld the constitutional validity of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 in the landmark ruling of *Swiss Ribbons v. Union of India*² in its entirety, thereby eradicating all the ambiguities. By relying on the statement of objects, the Preamble, and the comprehensive judicial background, the Hon'ble Court has presented a valuable perspective

² Ibid.

into the Code as an economic legislation, thereby putting to rest the Code's perplexing crudities and inequalities. In this case, the Court had been confronted with a multitude of obstacles challenging the constitutionality of the Code, the first and the most fundamental of which was the reasonable categorization of financial creditors and operational creditors. On this, the Apex Court after a meticulous assessment of the provisions of the Code, the Regulations, the Bankruptcy Law Reforms Committee Report, and the Insolvency Law Committee Report, 2018 ruled that the distinction between the two does not violate Article 14 of the Indian Constitution because the financial creditors have been implicated in evaluating the feasibility of the corporate debtors since the commencement of the Code. It further went on to state that in instances of financial distress, the financial creditors are the ones who indulge in loan restructuring and reorganization of the corporate debtor's firm, whereas on the other hand operational creditors are unlikely to do so. Therefore, with the intent of securing an optimum recovery for all the creditors, the Court concluded that there is an intelligible differentia between financial creditors and operational creditors. While observing that the bad debt crisis was rapidly deteriorating, the Supreme Court upheld the validity of Section 12A of the Code, which has as its basic notion the maximization of the value of the corporate debtor's assets in order to circumvent the procedural barriers. With respect to the issue of NCLT and NCLAT, the Supreme Court while relying on *Union of India v. R Gandhi*³ held permanent benches must be constituted at the seat of every jurisdictional High Court. Furthermore, the Court instructed the Union of India to set up circuit benches of NCLAT within a period of six months of the judgement's date to facilitate the Code's seamless implementation. The judgement talks at length about the appeal filed against Section 29 of the Code. The Hon'ble Court while relying on the judgements of *State Banks Staff Union (Madras Circle) v. Union of India*⁴ and *Arcelor Mittal India Pvt. Ltd. v. Satish Kumar Gupta and ors.*⁵ stated that the resolution applicants have no vested rights to be regarded as such in the resolution process. Furthermore, the Bench held that ineligibility under the provision is not confined to misconduct, as those who are regarded ineligible under the provision have been prohibited from purchasing assets of the corporate debtors whose obligations they have either willfully not paid, or they are unable to pay so. The Hon'ble Court citing the case of *Arcelor Mittal India Pvt. Ltd.*

³ Union of India v. R Gandhi , 2010 11 SCC 1.

⁴ State Banks Staff Union (Madras Circle) v. Union of India, 2005 7 SCC 584.

⁵ Arcelor Mittal India Pvt. Ltd. v Satish Kumar Gupta and ors , Civil appeal Nos. 9402-9405/2018.

*v Satish Kumar Gupta and ors.*⁶, stated that it is a settled law that a statute is not retrospective in nature plainly because it affects the vested rights or because a part of the prerequisites for its actions have been depicted from a time prior to its passage. As a result, the Court arrived at a conclusion that Section 29A of the Code continues to extend not just to the resolution applicants, but also to the liquidation applicants. Furthermore, in upholding the constitutionality of Section 53 of the Code, the Court held that the primary rationale for distinguishing between the financial debt and the operational debt is the relative prominence of the two types of debts in terms of the objectives of the Code. It went on to add that the rationale of repaying financial debts injects cash into the economy, which assists in lending such money to other entrepreneurs for their enterprises. Therefore, in lieu of this the Court held that Article 14 of the Indian Constitution will not be violated as long as there is some genuine interest that is sought to be safeguarded and is pertinent to the purpose of the Code. The Supreme Court concluded the judgement by asserting that there may be crudities and disparities in intricate pioneering economic legislation, but it cannot be knocked down as unconstitutional on that basis solely.

CASE COMMENT-:

From the aforementioned decision it can be concluded that the Supreme Court by upholding the constitutional validity of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 has created the groundwork for the Code's seamless implementation and efficiency of conducting business. Through this case, Justice RF Nariman has endeavored to unify India's insolvency law under a single uniform canopy with the intention of ramping up the insolvency process. In my opinion, the judgement has operated as a shining light in the corporate governance regime by strengthening the faith and the morale of investors and bidders in general through the objectives which have been set forth in the Code. It has buttressed the multitude of obstacles in the Code by laying a foundation for its reasoning. The Indian Judiciary, led by the Supreme Court has interpreted the provisions of the Code in a way that reflects the vision of the law and aids in its successful implementation. In the aforementioned judgement, the Hon'ble Court has firmly adhered to the notion of judicial hands off qua economic legislation, wherein the Court by functioning as a rescue operator, has mitigated the difficulties

⁶ Ibid.

which were being encountered by a corporate debtor, thus allowing the resolution process to operate efficiently. Furthermore, this landmark judgement has emphasized on the fact that the Supreme Court should consider situations in which the application of a legislative enactment appears to be arbitrary. Swiss Ribbons can be classified as the first step towards restoring the economy, as it provides long-overdue relief to investors, stakeholders, and creditors in the insolvency process. The case has not only upheld the constitutional validity of the Code, but also considered its economic ramifications in order to enhance a fair and an efficient insolvency process. As a result, the judgement has functioned as a ringing affirmation of the Code, wherein the defaulter's paradise has been forfeited and the economy has reclaimed its rightful perch. Penning down the decision, Justice RF Nariman hailed the Code as an economic and legislative initiative that passed constitutional scrutiny. Though the Bench through this landmark decision has reaffirmed the purpose of the Code by safeguarding the interest of all the stakeholders but it also had certain shortcomings. The Bench not only failed to clarify the dispute between Section 29A of the Code and Section 230 of the Companies Act, 2013 but also failed to provide the much-required clarity on the issue of the errant promoters entering through the back door. To conclude, I believe that there is still a long way to go and many more reforms in the areas of cross-border insolvency and stresses asset resolution are essential to facilitate the economic growth and development of the country.

